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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF EARTH SCIENCE SELF-LEARNING KIT (ESSLK) FOR GRADE 11

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Abstract

The study aimed to develop and validate Earth Science Self-Learning Kit (ESSLK) for Grade 11 students. In addition, the study employed true experimental research design and uses two groups of participants. The first group of participants involved the three (3) content experts and two (2) educational technology experts. They evaluated the ESSLK in terms of the printed module, video lessons, and manipulatives. On the other hand, the second group of participants included the sixty (60) Grade 11 STEM students in Holy Family Academy for the school year 2023-2024 who scored below the sixty percent (60%) passing score for the pretest served as the subject of the study. These participants were divided into two groups which consist of thirty (30) participants for the controlled group and thirty (30) participants for the experimental group using random sampling technique. Research findings revealed that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest score of the experimental group with a mean score of 39.60 (SD = 3.01), significantly surpassing the pretest mean score of 18.30 (SD = 3.26), $t(29) = 43.32$, $p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 7.91$. This meant that using the ESSLK improved the performance of the participants by reading the printed module, watching the video lessons, and utilizing the manipulatives. The study concluded that employing the developed and validated ESSLK encourages students to perform better and perceive the subject as more enjoyable. Therefore, it is recommended that teachers and administrators should encourage the implementation of self-directed learning strategies in teaching science to promote lifelong learning for the students.

Keywords: self-learning, printed module, video lessons, manipulatives, lifelong learning

INTRODUCTION

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Nothing remains constant in this world except for change. These profound words echo loudly in today's modern era, particularly within the context of education, where learners and their requirements are continually shifting and advancing. Today, teachers have to modernize their teaching practices to adapt to the varied range of students. It is essential for the teachers to embrace innovation and adapt their teaching strategies to ensure that every learner receives a meaningful and inclusive education. This innovation helps them identify the areas where learners need more help and provides support to improve their learning. The main focus lies in determining which innovation in education has the potential to cultivate a learning environment conducive to lifelong learning.

The COVID-19 pandemic has emerged as the largest disruptor in history, affecting schools worldwide due to their sudden closure of over 90 percent of the learner's population globally. This is exacerbated by the different challenges in education which results to worrisome of the learner's learning and mental well-being. With these pressing issues and challenges, the education sector should address these concerns to ensure quality and inclusive education for all learners (Natividad, 2021; Cano, 2022). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have emphasized the crucial role of education in their Goal 4: Quality Education which serves as a catalyst for sustainable development. This goal plays an important role in providing quality and inclusive education for all learners. This will be possible through innovative teaching strategies and techniques which cater to individual and diverse needs of the learners (United Nations, 2023).

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) under the Diversity of Learners (Domain 3) highly emphasize the individualized instruction (Department of Education, 2017). The teachers need to tailor their strategies to cater to the diverse needs of the learners. Through these efforts made by the teachers, the different learners with varying learning needs are given more attention. The teachers can also serve as scaffolding by guiding the learners in their personalized learning and provide targeted support to facilitate their learning experiences.

Recently, the Department of Education (DepEd) has implemented the Basic Education Learning Continuity (BE-LC) Plan. This plan was created in response to the challenges brought about by the pandemic because DepEd believes that education must continue amidst the pandemic. The creation of interventions is needed to assure the continuation of delivering quality education despite the pandemic. As required by Republic Act No. 10533 (2013), the state must build, maintain, and support a comprehensive, appropriate, and integrated educational system that meets the requirements of the people. As a result, meeting learners' shifting demands required the immediate invention, production, and dissemination of learning products.

With the shift to alternative delivery modes such as online, modular, and blended learning modalities, the demand for learning resources increased rapidly.

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Alternative approaches, such as sharing and reusing of modules among learners were encouraged to maximize utilization. Without sufficient resources, these learners faced difficulties in accessing and engaging with the curriculum, which could lead to learning gaps and hinder their educational progress. In the most recent International Student Assessment (PISA) and Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), the Philippines obtained the lowest science scores among all participating countries (DepEd, 2019; CNN Ph, 2020; Tagupa, 2019). This simply shows that learners have failed to master the required learning competencies to develop their problem-solving and critical-thinking skills.

Considering all these facts, the researcher observed that learners who have not mastered the essential learning competencies need immediate intervention. These learners have specific learning needs that necessitate specialized support based on the least learned competencies. As a result, developing a self-learning kit can be a valuable solution. A self-learning kit is a package of educational materials and resources that are designed to facilitate self-directed learning and provide learners with the necessary tools to take initiative in their own learning (Samia, 2020).

Hence, the researcher conducted this study to develop and validate an Earth Science Self-Learning Kit (ESSLK) for Grade 11 STEM students. Specifically, it aimed to validate the ESSLK in terms of experts' evaluation of the printed module, video lessons, and manipulatives. The researcher has also utilized the pretest and posttest scores of the participants for both controlled and experimental groups. Finally, the researcher has elaborated the implications of the study to further improve the science educational context.

Statement of the Objectives

The research aimed to develop and validate an Earth Science Self-Learning Kit (ESSLK) for Grade 11 STEM students.

Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Develop Earth Science Self-Learning Kit (ESSLK) for Grade 11 STEM students based on the least learned competencies.
2. Validate the developed Earth Science Self-Learning Kit (ESSLK) for Grade 11 STEM students in terms of:
 - 2.1. Experts' Evaluation
 - 2.2. Users' Evaluation
3. Determine the significant difference between the pretest of the control and experimental groups.

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4. Determine the significant difference between the posttest of the control and experimental groups.
5. Determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the control group.
6. Determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the experimental group.

METHODS

The study utilized a true experimental research design which includes the pretest and posttest gain scores of the participants which were divided into controlled and experimental groups. The study was conducted at Holy Family Academy of Angeles City, Inc. High School Department, which was located at Fil-Am Friendship Highway Cutcut, Angeles City. The first group of participants comprised three (3) Earth Science teachers and two (2) Educational technology experts. The second group of participants included sixty (60) Grade 11 SHS students which scored below sixty percent (60%) on the pretest. The 60 participants were divided into two groups, comprising 30 control group and 30 experimental group using the fishbowl method. The researcher used the Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMDS) Assessment and Evaluation of the Department of Education, particularly the evaluation rating sheet for print resources, video lessons, and manipulative materials. In this study, the researcher used the following statistical treatments:

2.1 Experts' Evaluation

(a) Mean and Standard Deviation. This was used to validate the results from the experts by calculating the mean and standard deviation to know the variation of the data set of the evaluation.

Table 1

Interpretation of the Mean Ratings on the Evaluation of the Printed Modules, Video Lessons, and Manipulatives.

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Scale	Mean rating interval	Description
4	3.25-4.00	Very Satisfactory
3	2.50-3.24	Satisfactory
2	1.75-2.49	Poor
1	1.00-1.74	Not Satisfactory

2.2. Users' Evaluation

The distribution of scores in pretest and posttest was examined to determine if it is normally distributed using Shapiro-Wilk test. Since the p-values in the pretest and posttest of control and experimental groups are greater than .05, the scores are normally distributed, that is why parametric statistics are more appropriate.

Table 2

Test for Normality

	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
Shapiro-Wilk W	0.963	0.979	0.979	0.946
Shapiro-Wilk p	0.362	0.808	0.804	0.131

(b) Independent t-Test. This was used to compare the pretest of the controlled and experimental group and posttest of the controlled and experimental group. It is an inferential statistical test used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups.

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(c) Paired Samples t-Test. This was used to compare the pretest and posttest scores of the controlled and experimental group. It is a type of t-test used to compare two sets of data that are related or matched in some way to determine if there is significant difference between them.

The data was analyzed using the SPSS software and Excel for statistical data analysis. After determining the comparison between the pretest and posttest scores of the controlled and experimental group, the researcher can find out whether the null hypotheses are rejected or not. If the p-value was less than 0.05, null hypothesis is rejected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Experts' Validation on the Developed ESSLK

Three (3) content experts and two (2) educational technology experts validated the printed module, video lessons, and manipulatives. Mean scores were computed to see if the ESSLK reached the minimum necessary points for each criterion.

Table 3

Summary of Mean Ratings from the Experts' Evaluation of the Printed Module, Video Lessons, and Manipulatives

Factors	Sum of Ratings	Min. and Max. Points		Remarks
Printed Modules				
1. Content	27.2	Min: 21.00	Max: 28.00	Passed
2. Format	70.60	Min: 54.00	Max: 72.00	Passed
3. Presentation and Organization	19.60	Min: 15.00	Max: 20.00	Passed
4. Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information	24.00	Min: 24.00	Max: 24.00	Passed
Video Lessons				
1. Content Quality	39.80	Min: 30.00	Max: 40.00	Passed
2. Instructional Quality	39.20	Min: 30.00	Max: 40.00	Passed
3. Technical Quality	51.80	Min: 39.00	Max: 52.00	Passed
4. Other Findings	16.00	Min: 16.00	Max: 16.00	Passed
Manipulatives				

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1. Content	39.60	Min: 30.00	Max: 40.00	Passed
2. Other Findings	16.00	Min: 16.00	Max: 16.00	Passed
3. Additional Requirements	23.60	Min: 18.00	Max: 24.00	Passed

B. Users' Evaluation on the Pretest and Posttest Scores on the Developed ESSLK

1. Comparison of pretest scores of control group and experimental group

Table 4

Comparison of Pretest Scores of Control Group and Experimental Group

Group	n	Mean	SD	t value	df	p value	Cohen's d	Decision
Control	30	17.90	3.66	0.52	58	0.60	0.14	Accept the H0
Experimental	30	18.30	3.26					

The results indicated that there was no significant difference between the pretest of control group ($M = 17.90$, $SD = 3.66$) and experimental group ($M = 18.30$, $SD = 3.26$), $t(58) = 0.52$, $p = 0.60$, Cohen's $d = 0.14$). The descriptive statistics revealed that the mean pre-test score for the control group was 17.90 with a standard deviation of 3.66, while for the experimental group, the mean pre-test score was slightly higher at 18.30 with a standard deviation of 3.26. Despite this mean difference of 0.47, the t-test yielded a t-value of 0.52 with 58 degrees of freedom, resulting in a p-value of 0.60. This p-value indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the pretest scores of the two groups. Moreover, the effect size, measured by Cohen's d , was calculated to be 0.14, indicating a small effect.

2. Comparison of Posttest Scores of Control Group and Experimental Group

Table 5

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Comparison of Posttest Scores of Control and Experimental Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	t value	df	p value	Cohen's d	Decision
Control	30	18.80	3.88	23.23	58	< .001	6.00	Reject the H0
Experimental	30	39.60	3.01					

The results indicated that there was a significant difference between the posttest of control group ($M = 18.80$, $SD = 3.88$ and experimental group ($M = 39.60$, $SD = 3.01$), $t(58) = 23.23$, $p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 6.00$). The descriptive statistics revealed that the mean posttest score for the control group was 18.80 with a standard deviation of 3.88, while for the experimental group, the mean posttest score was higher at 39.60 with a standard deviation of 3.01. Despite this mean difference of 20.8, the t-test yielded a t-value of 23.23 with 58 degrees of freedom, resulting in a p-value of $< .001$. This p-value indicates that there is statistically significant difference between the posttest scores of the two groups. Moreover, the effect size, measured by Cohen's d , was calculated to be 6.00, indicating a large effect.

3. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Control Group

Table 6

Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control Group

Test	N	Mean	SD	t value	df	p value	Cohen's d	Decision
Pretest	30	17.90	3.66	1.67	29	0.11	0.31	Accept the H0
Posttest	30	18.80	3.88					

The results indicated that the posttest mean score of the control group ($M = 18.80$, $SD = 3.88$) was not significantly higher than the pretest mean score ($M = 17.90$, $SD = 3.66$), $t(29) = 1.67$, $p = 0.11$, Cohen's $d = 0.31$). The results suggest that there was no significant difference between the posttest and pretest mean scores of the control group. While there was a slight increase in the posttest scores compared to the pretest scores, this difference was not large enough to be considered statistically significant, as indicated by the p-value being greater than 0.05. Additionally, the effect size (Cohen's d) suggests that any observed difference is small.

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4. Comparison of Pretest and Posttest scores of Experimental Group

Table 7

Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group

Test	N	Mean	SD	t value	df	p value	Cohen's d	Decision
Pretest	30	18.30	3.26	43.32	29	<.001	7.91	Reject the H0
Posttest	30	39.60	3.01					

The results indicated that the posttest mean score of the experimental group ($M = 39.60$, $SD = 3.01$) was significantly higher than the pretest mean score ($M = 18.30$, $SD = 3.26$), $t(29) = 43.32$, $p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 7.91$). The results suggest that the intervention implemented in the experimental group led to a significant improvement in the outcome measure. The mean score of participants in the experimental group increased from 18.30 (pretest) to 39.60 (posttest), with a very low probability ($p < 0.001$) of this change occurring due to chance alone. Additionally, the effect size (Cohen's $d = 7.91$) indicates a large and practically significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores. Therefore, it can be inferred that the ESSLK had a substantial positive effect on the outcome measure.

Conclusions

Drawing conclusions from the research findings, the following assertions emerge:

1. Before the intervention, all participants in the study exhibited similar levels of familiarity with the least developed skills in the field of Earth Science.
2. The findings indicated that participants who underwent the intervention achieved higher results compared to those taught in a traditional or conventional manner.
3. The results of the pretest and posttest scores of two distinct groups (control and manipulative), showed that both cohorts demonstrated learning, yet the manipulative group exhibited notably higher academic performance.
4. The researcher concluded that employing the developed and evaluated Earth Science Self-Learning Kit encourages students to perform better and perceive the subject as more enjoyable.

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Recommendations

The study revealed the effectiveness of the developed Earth Science Self-Learning Kit for Grade 11 Students. Consequently, the subsequent recommendations are put forth.

1. Integration of self-learning kits in diverse learning environments, including traditional classrooms, online platforms, and blended learning settings ensures accessibility for all students regardless of their learning preferences.
2. The implementation of self-directed learning strategies in teaching science to promote lifelong learning should be encouraged by the school administrators.
3. School administrators and teachers may subject the developed self-learning kit to quality assurance processes to assess its effectiveness before considering publication for the reproduction of printed copies.
4. Similar studies regarding the implementation of the self-learning kit must be conducted with a large group of students to determine whether the same findings will be drawn.
5. The researchers recommend that the ESSLK should be used in class instruction and secure copyright protection to safeguard intellectual property rights and ensure its sustained availability for educational purposes.

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